

Turbulence structure in a boundary layer wind tunnel

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Turbulence spectral analysis is a critical aspect of wind tunnel experiments. In this study, a modification of the Mann uniform shear model (M94), based on the Rapid Distortion theory (RDT), is proposed to adapt M94 for wind tunnel conditions and model the complete second-order turbulence structure. Firstly, the one-point spectra measured at heights ranging from 0.3 m to 1.5 m are analyzed. The total absolute error χ^2 for the modified M94 (M94-2) prediction is 0.998, compared to 1.6357 and 1.183 for M94 and the von Kármán spectral model, respectively; the results demonstrate the validity of the modification. Secondly, the spatial coherence is analyzed, with the spatial separations Δy and Δz ranging from 3.5 cm to 50 cm, M94-2 provides better predictions compared to the Krenk exponential coherence model. Notably, M94-2 is able to predict the turnaround of coherence at low wavenumber. Thirdly, the phase angle of the cross-spectrum for two vertically separated points is predicted by M94-2, M94-2 tends to overestimate the measurement due to noise contamination. In conclusion, the anisotropic spectrum of boundary layer wind tunnel turbulence can be modeled by M94-2 effectively with three parameters: $\alpha e^{2/3}$, L , and Γ , and the entire work is conducted within a unified theoretical framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

Turbulence spectral analysis, as a prerequisite for further estimation of dynamic loading on structures, is a fundamental process of wind tunnel tests. Complete second-order turbulence structure includes one-point auto-spectra $S_i(k_1)$, one-point cross-spectra $S_{ij}(k_1)$, $i \neq j$, and two-point cross-spectra $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$, where $i, j = u, v, w$ represent the longitudinal (x), lateral (y), and vertical (z) turbulence components, respectively. Here, $k_1 = 2\pi n/U$ is the longitudinal wavenumber, n is the frequency, and U is the mean wind speed. Besides $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$, the more often studied quantity is coherence $\text{coh}_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$ which is defined as:

$$\text{coh}_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \frac{|\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)|^2}{S_i(k_1)S_j(k_1)}. \quad (1)$$

To characterize the turbulence structure, numerous models have been proposed. Here we classify these models into three categories. The models in the first category are based on the isotropic homogeneous assumption, under which the isotropic homogeneous spectral tensor¹ $\Phi^{\text{iso}}(\mathbf{k})$ can be expressed analytically, grounded in a solid physical basis. Consequently, the spectrum can be also represented analytically (see more details in Sec. II A).

Wilson² compared three different forms of the isotropic model: the Gaussian model, the von Kármán model, and the Kolmogorov model, the result shows that the von Kármán

model is more realistic. Refs. 3–5 provided the analytical expressions for the coherence function using the isotropic tensor.

However, according to the assumption of homogeneity and isotropy, the one-point cross-spectrum should satisfy $S_{ij}(k_1) = 0, i \neq j$, and $S_v(k_1) = S_w(k_1)$. A typical observa-

FIG. 1. Typical one-point (cross-)spectra obtained from turbulence measurements in a boundary layer wind tunnel. S_u has more energy than S_v and S_w , even less. Cross-spectra are roughly zero except S_{uw} which is negative, see section III for details.

tion of the one-point spectrum, as shown in Fig. 1, reveals that the turbulence in the wind tunnel is not isotropic and homogeneous at large energy-containing scales. The isotropic homogeneous model is theoretically only valid within the inertial subrange and smaller scales, making anisotropic models essential to accurately represent the turbulence spectrum of

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TABLE I. Table of the notations in this paper.

$\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\} = \{u, v, w\}$	velocity vector	S_i, S_{ij}	one-point auto/cross-spectrum
$\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\} = \{x, y, z\}$	position vector	dZ_i	Fourier-Stieltjes integral of u_i
$\Delta y, \Delta z$	lateral and vertical spatial separation	Φ_{ij}	turbulence spectral tensor
$\mathbf{k} = \{k_1, k_2, k_3\}$	wavenumber vector	$E(k)$	spectrum of turbulent kinetic energy
k	magnitude of \mathbf{k}	κ	magnitude of horizontal wavenumbers
U	mean velocity	t, β	time and dimensionless time
u_*	friction velocity	τ	eddy lifetime
n	frequency	c_i^y, c_i^z	decay factor of the exponential coherence model
$f = nz/U$	Monin coordinate	α	the spectral Kolmogorov constant
$i, j = u, v, w$	subscript, denotes the turbulence component	ε	the rate of viscous dissipation
$\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$	two-points cross-spectrum	L, L_i	length scale and integral length scale
coh_{ij}	coherence	Γ	anisotropic parameter
χ^2	total absolute error	ϕ_{ij}	phase angle of χ_{ij}

the wind tunnel.

The second category is the semi-empirical model, such as the Simiu spectrum model⁶, the Kaimal spectrum model⁷, and the Davenport coherence model⁸. As summarized by Solari and Piccardo⁹, most of the spectrum models can be expressed as

$$\frac{nS_i(z, n)}{u_*^2} = \frac{A_i f^{a_i}}{(1 + B_i f^{b_i})^{c_i}}, \quad (2)$$

where A_i, B_i, a_i, b_i , and c_i are to be determined coefficients, $u_* = \sqrt{-\langle uw \rangle}$ is the friction velocity, $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes ensemble averaging, $f = nz/U$ is the Monin coordinate.

The von Kármán spectral model is also widely used as an empirical model by assigning a different length scale to each turbulence component. This erodes the simplicity of the isotropic von Kármán model and makes it anisotropic even at the smallest scales. It also hinders the very efficient field generation algorithm used for the original isotropic von Kármán model and the Mann model¹⁰.

Instead of calculating $\text{coh}_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$ using the definition in Eq. (1), Davenport⁸ proposed the exponential coherence function to compute $\text{coh}_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$ directly. To improve the efficacy, several other exponential models have been proposed, such as the Jakobsen coherence model¹¹, and the Krenk coherence model¹². Zeng et al.¹³ tested the isotropic coherence model and those semi-empirical coherence models. The results indicate that the isotropic model performs relatively well only for small spatial separation, while the Krenk coherence model shows better accuracy under wind tunnel conditions. Therefore, the Krenk model will be used as a reference for comparison with the model proposed in this paper. The Krenk coherence model is formulated as follows:

$$\text{coh}_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_1}{2} \sqrt{(c_i^y \Delta y)^2 + (c_i^z \Delta z)^2}\right) \exp\left(-\kappa_1 \sqrt{(c_i^y \Delta y)^2 + (c_i^z \Delta z)^2}\right), \quad (3)$$

where c_i^y and c_i^z are the decay factor, $\kappa_1 = \sqrt{L_u^{-2} + k_1^2}$, L_u is the longitudinal integral length scale. It can be seen that to model the second-order structure of turbulence fully, the semi-empirical model necessitates an extensive set of parameters.

The third category is based on Rapid Distortion Theory^{1,14} (RDT), in which the models are expressed in more complicated integral forms compared to the first and second categories. Mann¹⁵ initially proposed two models based on RDT for neutral atmospheric boundary layer, which assume the turbulence field is homogeneous and vertically inhomogeneous, respectively. The homogeneous model (denoted as M94 hereafter) has simpler expressions and has been widely adopted to analyze atmospheric boundary layer turbulence spectra, to calculate loads on wind turbines¹⁶, and is codified in the IEC¹⁷

standard for the design of wind turbines¹⁷. M94 has been used to load calculations on other structures⁹ but its application to boundary layer wind tunnel turbulence investigations is limited despite early work on bridge-aerodynamics in the boundary layer wind tunnel of the Danish Maritime Institute¹⁸.

In subsequent work, the model was generalized into stably stratified atmospheric boundary layer, as proposed by Segalini et al.¹⁹ and Chougule et al.²⁰, respectively. The key advantage of M94 is that the second-order turbulence structure of a local turbulence field is fully decided by three parameters. Addition generalizations include not only spatial correlations but also temporal and spatial correlations^{21,22} that have applications in lidar-assisted wind turbine control²³.

However, the original M94 faces challenges in predicting

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the large-scale structure within the energy-containing range under wind tunnel conditions. This paper proposes a new eddy lifetime function to replace the original in M94, the modified M94 successfully represents the complete second-order structure of boundary layer wind tunnel turbulence.

In Sec. II, we briefly introduce the isotropic tensor with the von Kármán model, RDT, and M94, followed by a modification of M94 tailored for wind tunnel conditions. In Sec. III, we present the measurements in XNJD-3 boundary layer wind tunnel and the predictions based on the models discussed.

II. METHOD

A. Isotropic turbulence spectrum model and the von Kármán model

Consider a three-dimensional turbulence field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \{u_1(\mathbf{x}), u_2(\mathbf{x}), u_3(\mathbf{x})\} = \{u(\mathbf{x}), v(\mathbf{x}), w(\mathbf{x})\}$ and its Fourier-Stieltjes integral:

$$dZ_i(\mathbf{k}) = \int u_i(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} d\mathbf{x}, \quad (4)$$

where the integration is over all physical space. $dZ_i(\mathbf{k})$ is connected to $\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k})$ by

$$\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{\langle dZ_i^*(\mathbf{k}) dZ_j(\mathbf{k}) \rangle}{dk_1 dk_2 dk_3}, \quad (5)$$

where superscript * denotes complex conjugation. For a different notation see Batchelor²⁴.

With the assumption of isotropy, the isotropic tensor Φ_{ij}^{iso} can be expressed as¹

$$\Phi_{ij}^{\text{iso}}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{E(k)}{4\pi k^4} (\delta_{ij} k^2 - k_i k_j), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{k} = \{k_1, k_2, k_3\}$ is the wavenumber vector, $k = \sqrt{k_1^2 + k_2^2 + k_3^2}$, $E(k)$ is the energy spectrum, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta function. $E(k)$ suggested by von Kármán²⁵ is

$$E(k) = \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3} L^{5/3} \frac{(kL)^4}{(1 + (kL)^2)^{17/6}}, \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha \approx 1.7$ is the spectral Kolmogorov constant, ε is the rate of viscous dissipation of specific turbulent kinetic energy, L is a length scale.

In general, the spectral tensor of the turbulence fluctuations $\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k})$ has the following relationship¹⁵ with the one-point auto- ($i = j$) or cross- ($i \neq j$) spectrum $S_{ij}(k_1)$ and the two-point cross-spectrum $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)$:

$$S_{ij}(k_1) = \int \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) d\mathbf{k}_\perp \quad (8)$$

and

$$\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \int \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) e^{i(k_2 \Delta y + k_3 \Delta z)} d\mathbf{k}_\perp, \quad (9)$$

where $\int d\mathbf{k}_\perp = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk_2 dk_3$. Then the one-point spectrum of the von Kármán model can be derived:

$$S_u(k_1) = \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3} \frac{9}{55} \frac{1}{(L^{-2} + k_1^2)^{5/6}}, \quad (10)$$

$$S_i(k_1) = \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3} \frac{3}{110} \frac{3L^{-2} + 8k_1^2}{(L^{-2} + k_1^2)^{11/6}} \quad \text{for } i = v, w.$$

To use the von Kármán model to predict the anisotropic turbulence spectrum, L_i , the length scale in each direction, should replace L in Eq. (10).

B. Basic equations of RDT

Within RDT, the mean velocity is assumed as uniform shear, i.e. $U(\mathbf{x}) = \{z dU/dz, 0, 0\}$, where dU/dz is a constant. For the sake of brevity, here we will directly give the governing equations of $dZ_i(\mathbf{k}, \beta)$ based on RDT, see more details in Ref. 1 and 15:

$$\frac{\partial dZ_i(\mathbf{k}, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = \left(-\delta_{i1} + 2 \frac{k_i k_1}{k^2} \right) dZ_3(\mathbf{k}, t), \quad (11)$$

where $\beta = t dU/dz$ is non-dimensional time, t is time. To get Eq. (11), the time evolution property of wavenumber space is used, which is formulated as

$$\frac{dk_i}{dt} = -k_j \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i}. \quad (12)$$

It reveals that the wavenumber space is distorted by the mean shear, and this effect is the primary cause of the anisotropy in the shear flow. Combining with the uniform shear assumption, we get initial condition of $\mathbf{k}_0 = \{k_1, k_2, k_3\}$ and its state at β : $\mathbf{k} = \{k_1, k_2, k_3\}$, where $k_3 = k_{30} - k_1 \beta$. The solution of Eq. (11) is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} dZ_1(\mathbf{k}, \beta) \\ dZ_2(\mathbf{k}, \beta) \\ dZ_3(\mathbf{k}, \beta) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \psi_1 \\ 0 & 1 & \psi_2 \\ 0 & 0 & k_0^2/k^2 \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} dZ_1(\mathbf{k}_0, 0) \\ dZ_2(\mathbf{k}_0, 0) \\ dZ_3(\mathbf{k}_0, 0) \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

where

$$\psi_1 = C_1 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} C_2, \quad \psi_2 = \frac{k_2}{k_1} C_1 + C_2,$$

$$C_1 = \frac{\beta k_1^2 (k_0^2 - 2k_{30}^2 + \beta k_1 k_{30})}{\kappa^2 k^2}, \quad (14)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{k_2 k_0^2}{\kappa^3} \arctan\left(\frac{\beta k_1 \kappa}{k_0^2 - k_{30} k_1 \beta}\right),$$

$$\kappa = \sqrt{k_1^2 + k_2^2}.$$

C. Eddy lifetime, Mann uniform shear model and its modification

Eq. (14) describes the transient linear process of uniform shear flow, where the eddies will be stretched infinitely over

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FIG. 2. The difference of $\tau_1(k)$, $\tau_2(k)$, and $\tau_3(k)$, $\Gamma = 1$ in the plot. k is nondimensionalized by L , and τ is dimensionless time.

time, which is unrealistic. According to energy cascade theory¹, eddies will break up at some point, to model this process and effectively make the model stationary, thereby making it independent of time, Mann¹⁵ proposed substituting β with a k -dependent eddy lifetime function $\tau(k)$.

On the scale of the inertial subrange and the smaller scale,²¹⁸ where the turbulence is homogeneous and isotropic, Landau and Lifshitz²⁶ show that

$$\tau_1(k) \propto \varepsilon^{-1/3} k^{-2/3}. \quad (15)$$

On the scale larger than the inertial subrange, Mann pro-²¹⁹ posed that $\tau_2(k) \approx k^{-1} (\int_k^\infty E(p) dp)^{-1/2}$, substitute $E(k)$ with²²⁰ Eq. (7), one can get

$$\tau_2(k) = \Gamma \left(\frac{dU}{dz} \right)^{-1} (kL)^{-2/3} \left[{}_2F_1 \left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{17}{6}; \frac{4}{3} - (kL)^{-2} \right) \right]^{-1/2}, \quad (16)$$

where Γ is an anisotropy parameter to be determined, ${}_2F_1$ ²²⁵ is the hypergeometric function. It shows that the eddy lifetime is controlled by the turbulent kinetic energy of the eddies whose scale is smaller than k , a similar result can also be found in Ref. [27]. It can be seen that $\tau_2(k) \propto k^{-2/3}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, which is consistent with $\tau_1(k)$, and $\tau_2(k) \propto k^{-1}$ as $k \rightarrow 0$.

Given the isotropic initial condition $\Phi_{ij}(k, 0) = \Phi_{ij}^{\text{iso}}(k)$ as the von Kármán spectrum, the expression of homogeneous anisotropic turbulence spectral tensor $\Phi_{ij}(k, \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}, L, \Gamma)$ based on M94 can be formulated by combining Eq. (5) and (14). So, the von Kármán spectrum can be regarded as a special case of M94 when $\Gamma = 0$. According to Eq. (14), we can get:

$$\begin{aligned} dZ_i(k_1, k_2, k_3, \beta) &= dZ_i(k_1, -k_2, k_3, \beta) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 3, \\ dZ_2(k_1, k_2, k_3, \beta) &= -dZ_2(k_1, -k_2, k_3, \beta), \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

therefore, among all the components of one-point cross-spectra, only $S_{uv}(k_1)$ is non-zero, the measurements (as shown in Fig. 1) also support that conclusion.

However, the original M94 has difficulties in predicting

the turbulence structure in wind tunnel as will be shown in Sec. III. The reason is that, compared to atmospheric boundary layer turbulence, the turbulence field in a wind tunnel more closely resembles channel flow with finite upstream fetch. To address the issue, we adopt a new expression $\tau_3(k)$. $\tau_3(k)$ should also satisfy that $\tau_3(k) \propto k^{-2/3}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. For sufficiently small k corresponding to large eddies, $\tau_3(k)$ should be uniformly limited, because the development and stretching of large-scale eddies are constrained by the geometry of the wind tunnel, hence, $\tau_3(k)$ tend to a constant as $k \rightarrow 0$, so we propose

$$\tau_3(k) \propto \frac{1}{(1 + (kL)^{-2})^{1/3}} \quad (18)$$

For comparison with M94, two more expressions of eddy lifetime function based on the above discussion are tested, the first one (denoted as M94-1 hereafter) is

$$\tau_1(k) = \Gamma \left(\frac{dU}{dz} \right)^{-1} (kL)^{-2/3}, \quad (19)$$

the second one (denoted as M94-2 hereafter) is

$$\tau_3(k) = \Gamma \left(\frac{dU}{dz} \right)^{-1} (1 + (kL)^2)^{-1/3}. \quad (20)$$

The difference of $\tau_1(k)$, $\tau_2(k)$, and $\tau_3(k)$, as shown in Fig. 2, remains on the large scale where $k_1 L < 1$. The results in Sec. III will show that M94-2 performs best in predicting the turbulence structure in the boundary layer wind tunnel.

To conclude, the local second-order turbulence structure is fully decided by $\Phi_{ij}(k, \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}, L, \Gamma)$. Using Eq. (8) and (9), one-point (cross-)spectrum, two-point cross-spectrum, and coherence can be modeled within a unified framework.

FIG. 3. Overview of the wind tunnel setup and experimental condition. y and z are the coordinates. Δy is the lateral separation.

227 III. RESULTS

228 A. Experimental setup

229 The experiment was carried out in an extremely large
230 boundary layer wind tunnel (XNJD-3) at Southwest Jiao-
231 tong University¹³, the size of the working section is 22.5 m
232 (width)×4.5 m (height). The three-dimensional velocity fluct-
233 uations were measured by Cobra Probe located at the center
234 of the working section of the wind tunnel. The turbulence is
235 generated by the spires 23 m upstream.

236 The environment of the wind tunnel is shown in Fig. 3, two
237 sets of probes were used to sample the turbulence fluctuations
238 \mathbf{u} , the sampling frequency is 256 Hz, and the acquisition time
239 is 2 min.

240 To test the discussed models, two experiments are con-

241 ducted. As shown in Fig. 4, the turbulence spectrum and lat-
242 eral coherence are measured at $z=0.91$ m, with the lateral sep-
243 aration Δy ranging from 3.5 cm to 50 cm. For comparison with
244 M94-2, the von Kármán model, M94, and M94-1 are used to
245 model the one-point (cross-)spectrum, while the Krenk coher-
246 ence model is used to model the lateral coherence. To validate
247 the ability of M94-2 to predict vertical coherence and to test
248 the influence of height, the turbulence spectrum and vertical
249 coherence are measured at different heights. The heights of
250 the lower probe z_1 are set at 30 cm, 70 cm, and 120 cm, re-
251 spectively, while the height of the higher probe $z_2 = z_1 + \Delta z$,
252 with vertical separation Δz are set to 10 cm, 15 cm, 20 cm,
253 and 30 cm, respectively.

254 To find the parameters of M94, M94-1 and M94-2 to the
255 data, a χ^2 -fit, as suggested by Mann¹⁵, is performed by min-
256 imizing the total absolute error:

$$\chi^2(\Gamma, L, \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}) = \sum_{j=1}^N (S_{u_{w,t}}(k_j) - S_{u_{w,t}}(k_j))^2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^N (S_{i,t}(k_j) - S_i(k_j))^2. \quad (21)$$

270 FIG. 4. The diagram of the data processing procedure, where FT
271 stands for Fourier transform. The parameters of M94-2 are obtained
272 by fitting the turbulence spectrum, using which the coherence is fur-
273 ther calculated.

257 To fit the data with the von Kármán spectrum model and
258 the Krenk coherence model, each one-point component spec-
259 trum and coherence is fitted to the model independently giv-
260 ing rise to a multitude of fitting parameters while the Mann
261 model only has three parameters fitting all one-point compo-
262 nent spectra and predicting the two-point statistics.

264 B. One-point spectrum

265 As discussed before, to model the anisotropic turbulence
266 spectrum using the von Kármán model, single length scale L
267 in Eq. (10) should be replaced by the integral length scale L_i
268 in each direction. Besides, the von Kármán model cannot be
269 used to model $S_{uw}(k_1)$ directly. As suggested by Solari and
270 Piccardo⁹, $S_{uw}(k_1)$ has the following relationship with $S_u(k_1)$
271 and $S_w(k_1)$:

272 Solari and Piccardo⁹ suggest that

$$S_{uw}(n) = c \frac{\sqrt{S_u(n)S_w(n)}}{\sqrt{1 + 0.4(nL_w/U)}}, \quad (22)$$

$$c = -\frac{u_*^2}{\sigma_u \sigma_w 1.11 (L_w/L_u)^{0.21}}. \quad (23)$$

273 However, in practice, we found that using Eq. (23) tends to
274 overestimate $S_{uw}(k_1)$, we propose that c should be treated as
275 an independent parameter. The measurements and fitting re-
276 sults from different models are shown in Fig. 5, the parameters
277 of M94-2 and the von Kármán model are shown in Table II
278 and Table III, respectively, the χ^2 values of different models
279 are shown in Table IV.

TABLE II. The parameters of M94-2.

$\alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}$ [$\text{m}^{3/4} \text{s}^{-2}$]	L [m]	Γ [-]
1.402	0.726	3.050

TABLE III. The parameters of the von Kármán model.

$\alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}$ [$\text{m}^{3/4} \text{s}^{-2}$]	L_u [m]	L_v [m]	L_w [m]	c [-]
1.247	1.491	1.009	0.895	-0.497

TABLE IV. The χ^2 value of different model.

model	von Kármán model	M94	M94-1	M94-2
χ^2	1.1839	1.6375	1.1875	0.9982

280 As a benchmark, the von Kármán model can fit the turbu-
281 lence spectra well, especially $S_{uw}(k_1)$ at high wavenumber,
282 meanwhile, it underestimates the peak of $S_{uw}(k_1)$. In com-
283 parison, M94 cannot accurately predict the turbulence spectra

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FIG. 5. The measurements (WT) of one-point (cross-)spectra and the model spectra based on M94, M94-1, M94-2, and the von Kármán spectral model.

FIG. 6. The parameters of M94-2 at different heights.

at low wavenumber. By modifying $\tau(k)$, significant improve-
 286 ments are achieved, M94-2 has the best agreement with the
 287 measurements among all the models tested in this study con-
 288 cerning the value of χ^2 .
 289

We further test the models at different heights ranging from
 290 30 cm to 150 cm, M94-2 also gives the best agreements,
 291 the parameters of M94-2 along height are shown in Fig. 6.
 292 According to the homogeneous assumption, the parameters
 293 should not change with the position of measurement. In prac-
 294 tice, the assumption is correct in the horizontal direction, how-
 295 ever, the parameters do vary vertically. ϵ gives the amplitude
 296 of the inertial subrange of the turbulence spectrum²⁸. In at-
 297 mospheric boundary layer, $\epsilon = u_*^3 / (\kappa_0 z)$, where $\kappa_0 \approx 0.4$ is
 298 the von Kármán constant, decreases with height. By contrast,
 299 ϵ increases with z in the wind tunnel boundary layer, it may
 300 be due to that the turbulence boundary layer is not fully devel-
 301 oped. Like L_i corresponding to the peak of $S_i(k_1)$, L , as
 302 a length scale of turbulence field, corresponds to the peak of
 303 turbulent kinetic energy spectra. In the atmospheric boundary
 304 layer, $L \propto z$, however, in the wind tunnel, L increases with z
 305 until $z \approx 1.1$ m, this may be caused by the distribution and the
 306 characteristics of the upstream spires. Γ exhibits an opposite
 307 trend to L in its variation with height, it shows that $\tau(k)$ will
 308 not change fast with the increase of height.

at low wavenumber. By modifying $\tau(k)$, significant improve-
 286 ments are achieved, M94-2 has the best agreement with the
 287 measurements among all the models tested in this study con-
 288 cerning the value of χ^2 .
 289

FIG. 7. The measured lateral coherence and the model results based M94-2 and the Krenk coherence model are shown, respectively. c_i is the decay factor defined in Eq. (3).

311 As will be shown in the following sections, M94-2 can also
 312 effectively represent the vertical coherence and the phase angle
 313 of $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)$. It indicates that homogeneous as-
 314 sumption remains valid at a certain scale.

315 **C. Spatial coherence**

316 Based on the parameters obtained in Sec. III B, the coher-
 317 ence can be calculated directly by the following equation:

$$318 \text{coh}_{ij}(\bar{k}_1, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \frac{|\chi_{ij}(\bar{k}_1, \Delta y, \Delta z, \alpha \bar{\epsilon}^{2/3}, \bar{L}, \bar{\Gamma})|^2}{S_i(\bar{k}_1, \alpha \bar{\epsilon}^{2/3}, \bar{L}, \bar{\Gamma}) S_j(\bar{k}_1, \alpha \bar{\epsilon}^{2/3}, \bar{L}, \bar{\Gamma})}, \quad (24)$$

319 where \bar{k}_1 , $\bar{\epsilon}$, \bar{L} , and $\bar{\Gamma}$ are the mean of k_1 , ϵ , L , and Γ of
 320 the two measured points. As discussed before, the parameters
 321 are only dependent on z . For horizontal coherence, k_1 and the
 322 parameters are the same at the two points. For vertical coher-
 323 ence, the parameters are the average at two different heights,
 324 and $\bar{k}_1 = 4\pi n / (U(z_1) + U(z_2))$.

325 The measured horizontal coherence and the model results
 326 based on M94-2 and the Krenk coherence model are shown in
 327 Fig. 7. As the result shows, the Krenk model has difficulty in
 328 predicting $\text{coh}_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y)$ when Δy is small. The decay factor c_i
 329 varies with Δy and differs across components, and there is no
 330 reliable method for determining the appropriate c_i other than
 331 through experiment.

332 In comparison, $\text{coh}_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y)$ can be directly estimated using
 333 M94-2 by applying Eq. (24) together with the one-point spec-
 334 trum results, without requiring any additional information.
 335 The result shows that M94-2 can well predict $\text{coh}_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y)$, ex-
 336 cept when the coherence (e.g., $\text{coh}_{ww}(k_1, \Delta y = 0.5)$) is dimi-
 337 nished. With the increase of spatial separation, $\text{coh}_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y)$
 338 decays, the noise signal is more prominent in the measure-
 339 ments, which further weakens the coherence, when coherence
 340 is relatively low, the model results tend to overestimate the
 341 measurements.

342 The results of vertical coherence $\text{coh}_{ii}(k_1, \Delta z)$ and the influ-
 343 ence of probe height are presented in Fig. 8. The results vali-
 344 date the ability of M94-2 to characterize the vertical coherence

FIG. 8. The measured vertical coherence at different heights and the model results based M94-2 are shown. The dashed lines represent the measurements, and the solid lines represent the model results.

of wind tunnel turbulence. For small Δz , $\text{coh}_{ij}(k_1, \Delta z)$ is not affected by $\bar{z} = (z_1 + z_2)/2$. With increasing Δz , in comparison between the first and third columns, smaller \bar{z} corresponds to lower coherence. As \bar{L} increases with \bar{z} , consequently, the coherence is enhanced due to the stronger correlation over larger spatial scales.

It should also be noted that the coherence is not monotonically decreasing with respect to k_1 , the coherence (particularly for v and w components) would turn around at low wavenumber. Such phenomena cannot be predicted by the exponential coherence function, but it is captured by M94-2.

D. Phase angle of cross-spectrum

Both the value of one-point and two-point cross-spectrum can be complex. As mentioned in Sec.III B, $S_{uv}(k_1)$ is the only non-zero one-point cross-spectrum. According to the homogeneous assumption, it can be further deduced that $\Im\{S_{uv}(k_1)\} = 0$, which is also consistent with both the mea-

surements and the prediction of M94-2. Furthermore, for unstably stratified atmospheric boundary layer which is vertically inhomogeneous, $\Im\{S_{uv}(k_1)\}$ is also non-zero²⁹.

The cases of $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z = 0)$ and $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)$ are different. Specifically, with reference to Eq. (5), Eq. (9), Eq. (13), (14), and Eq. (17), it can be proven that the imaginary part of $\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z = 0)$ satisfies

$$\Im\{\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z = 0)\} = \int \sin(k_2 \Delta y) \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) d\mathbf{k}_\perp = 0. \quad (25)$$

By contrast, $\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}, L, \Gamma)$ is neither odd nor even with respect to k_3 , so³⁰

$$\Im\{\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)\} = \int \sin(k_3 \Delta z) \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) d\mathbf{k}_\perp \neq 0. \quad (26)$$

To elaborate, the evolution of wavenumber space, as revealed in Eq. (12), can be explained as a consequence of the anisotropy of the turbulent field distorted by shear. Hence, $\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \alpha \varepsilon^{2/3}, L, \Gamma)$ is not symmetric with respect to $k_3 = 0$,

FIG. 9. The measured $\varphi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta z)$ at different heights and the model results based M94-2. The dashed lines represents the measurements, and the solid lines represents the model results.

376 then the phase delay of $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$ arises at different heights, i.e.,³⁸⁹
 377 the phase angle of $\chi_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)$. Using M94-2, the phase
 378 angle of vertical two-point cross-spectrum $\varphi_{ii}(k_1, \Delta z)$ can be
 379 calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{ij} &= \arg[\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)] \\ &= \arctan \frac{\Re\{\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)\}}{\Im\{\chi_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)\}}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

380 Intuitively, the phase angle is due to the fact that in shear tur-
 381 bulance, fluctuations tend to arrive first to the upper measure-
 382 ment point and later to the lower point.

383 The results are shown in Fig. 9. In the measure-
 384 ments, $\Re\{\chi_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)\} \gg \Im\{\chi_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)\}$,
 385 $\Im\{\chi_{ii}(k_1, \Delta y = 0, \Delta z)\}$ is very small and easily contaminated⁴⁰²
 386 by noise as the coherence for large spatial separation. As a
 387 result, the value is relatively overestimated by M94-2, partic-
 388 ularly for large k_1 .⁴⁰³

IV. CONCLUSION

391 In this study, a modification of the Mann uniform shear
 392 model, by adopting a new expression of the eddy lifetime
 393 $\tau(k)$, has been presented to model the complete second-order
 394 turbulence structure of wind tunnel turbulence, including the
 395 one-point (cross-)spectra, spatial coherence, and the phase
 396 angle of the two-point cross-spectrum with vertical separation.
 397 The results of the wind tunnel turbulence structure measured
 398 in the XNJD-3 wind tunnel have been used to test M94-2.
 399 The results show that M94-2 performs best compared to M94,
 400 M94-1, the von Kármán spectral model, and the Krenk coher-
 401 ence model. M94-2 contains three parameters: $\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}$, L , and Γ .

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